

Qualitative Study on Dynamics of Ethnic Fragmentation and Violence in Plateau State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This research explores the intricate relationship between the quantitative study on dynamic ethnic fragmentation and violence in Plateau State, Nigeria, a region marked by historical tensions and conflicts. As a microcosm of Nigeria's diverse ethnic landscape, Plateau State presents a compelling case for examining how ethnic identities intersect with socio-political dynamics to fuel violence. Despite existing literature on ethnic conflict in Nigeria, there remains a significant gap in understanding the specific interplay of these factors in Plateau State, particularly regarding local governance and its role in exacerbating or mitigating tensions. Employing a mixed-methods approach, the study integrates quantitative data analysis with qualitative interviews to uncover the underlying causes of conflict. Key factors such as competition for resources, political marginalization, and historical grievances are analyzed to understand their roles in exacerbating ethnic divisions. The research highlights how local power dynamics and external influences contribute to cycles of violence, revealing the complexities of inter-ethnic relations and the impact of group identity on conflict behavior. Furthermore, this study aims to assess existing peace building initiatives and propose actionable recommendations for policymakers and community leaders. By situating Plateau State within broader regional and national contexts, this research contributes to academic discourse on ethnic conflict and offers practical solutions for fostering stability in ethnically diverse societies. Ultimately, the findings underscore the urgent need for targeted interventions that address the root causes of violence while promoting social cohesion and mutual understanding among ethnic groups.

Keywords: Ethnic Fragmentation, Conflict, Violence, Ethnic Identities, Political Marginalization

Introduction

Conflict is a global phenomenon; for ages, individuals, state actors, and non-state actors have been confronting different forms of conflict. Nigeria, with over 250 ethnic groups and different religious affiliations, has been facing ethnic fragmentation and violence (Onyekachukwu & Oghogho, 2018; Mbah et al., 2019; Chidozie & Orji, 2022). One of the major hotspots of ethnic fragmentation and violence in Nigeria is Plateau State (Nyam, 2017; Mbah et al., 2019). The state, once known for peace and tolerance, has, in recent decades been marred by recurrent ethno-religious violence, particularly in the city of Jos, where tensions between indigene groups and settler communities have escalated (Gyang, 2023).

Plateau State in Nigeria is characterized by a significant population of ethnic minorities, with over 58 relatively small ethnic communities identified during the Plateau State Peace Conference in 2004, spanning its 17 Local Government areas (Best, 2007). These indigenous ethnic groups can be broadly categorized into the Agro-Ashanti and the Benue-Congo language groups. The indigenous ethnic groups in Plateau State, Nigeria, can be categorized into two main language groups, namely the Afro-Ashantic speakers, which include the Ngas, Mwaghavul, Mupun, Goemai, Montol, Ron, Kulere, Doemak, Mernyang, FierMushere, among others (Plateau State Government, 2001), and the Benue-Congo speakers, which comprise the Berom, Afezere, Naraguta, Ganawuri, Miyango, Erigwe, and others. Additionally, there are various incoming ethnic groups, such as the Hausa/Fulani, Yoruba, Igbo, Urhobo, Nupe, Kanuri, Idoma, and Tiv. The implications of the ethnic plurality in Plateau State are fragmentation and violence. Therefore, Plateau State, previously recognized for its reputation of peace, tolerance, and harmony among indigenes and settlers, has recently experienced a surge of hatred, hostility, and violence. The prolonged communal in the State, particularly in its capital city of Jos, has evolved from a political crisis centered around 'indigene' rights

and political representation over the past two decades, subsequently impacting various state regions (Gyang, 2023). For instance, the Afizere, Anaguta, and Berom, considered indigenous and primarily Christian, and the Hausa and Fulani, considered settlers and primarily Muslims, are the main parties to the conflict. Over the years, violent conflict has been documented across communities in the State, since 2013 to 2023.(Yahuza, 2023; Plateau State Peace Building Agency, 2022).

The reoccurring conflicts in the State are caused by multifaceted factors, including long-standing tensions between indigenes and settlers, ethnic and religious groups, and disputes over scarce resources. However, efforts by the federal and state governments to mitigate the surge of the conflict have not been effective. In most cases, the government's actions include kinetic and non-kinetic approaches, such as deploying security agencies, setting up a probe panel, and establishing the Plateau State Peace building Agency (Marie-Therese, 2023; Yahuza, 2023). However, the effective execution of government measures has been hindered by security agencies responsible for their implementation. Furthermore, the utilization of vigilante groups to combat the recurrent crisis in the state has resulted in complications, particularly in cases where extrajudicial killings have incited retaliatory actions. Although such efforts have decreased violence, ethnic and religious tensions, suspicions, and hatred remain prevalent throughout the state. Against the background of ethnic complexities of Plateau State, this article examines the roots of ethnic fragmentation and violence in Plateau State. The study highlights how these drivers continue to incite violence and explores potential pathways to sustainable peace, it also identify and analyses the key socio-political, economic, and historical factors contributing to ethnic fragmentation and violence in Plateau State; to explore the dynamics of inter-ethnic relations in Plateau State, focusing on how these relationships influence patterns of conflict and cooperation; to assess existing peace building initiatives and their effectiveness in addressing the root causes of ethnic conflict in Plateau State; and to propose actionable recommendations for policymakers and community leaders aimed at promoting social cohesion, reconciliation, and sustainable peace in ethnically diverse environments.

Despite extensive literature on ethnic conflict in Nigeria, a significant gap exists in understanding the interplay between ethnic fragmentation and violence specifically in Plateau State. Most studies generalize the issue without exploring the unique socio-political dynamics and historical contexts of the region (Gutierrez, 2020; Ruane & Todd, 2026). Additionally, they often overlook the role of local governance in either exacerbating or mitigating ethnic tensions. To address this gap, this research will focus on Plateau State using a mixed-methods approach to provide a nuanced analysis that incorporates local perspectives. By examining inter-ethnic relationships and resource competition, the study aims to clarify the complexities of conflict dynamics. Furthermore, the effectiveness of current peace building initiatives will be assessed, leading to tailored recommendations for the affected communities. This research seeks to enhance the understanding of ethnic conflict in Nigeria and offer practical solutions for fostering social cohesion and sustainable peace.

Ethnic Fragmentation in Plateau State

Ethnicity is a complex concept with no universally accepted definition. Uzoigwe & Nwadiolor (2017) trace the etymology of "ethnic" to the Greek word "ethnos," which refers to a group sharing a distinct culture. Culture is defines ethnicity as a social phenomenon emerging from interactions among individuals from different ethnic backgrounds, highlighting shared cultural identities and communal bonds (Ruane & Todd, 2016; Taras & Ganguly, 2015). According to Peters (2006), the term "fragmentation" has a negative meaning and is used as a pejorative. Fragmentation threatens unity, harmony, cohesiveness, and order. Therefore, ethnic fragmentation can be described as the negative division experienced by peoples from different ethnic backgrounds who live in the same community, nation, state, or country. This study adopts the term "ethnic fragmentation" to describe the negative divisions among different ethnic groups living within the same community or nation. Peters (2006) asserts that fragmentation threatens unity and cohesion, a concern evident in Nigeria, where ethnic fragmentation correlates with increased risks of internal violence (Erhirhie & Okereka, 2024).

Conflict in Plateau State

The Term "Conflict," The Term "Conflict," originating from the Latin "conflictus," signifies a clash between opposing forces (Abasili et al., 2023). According to Schmid (1998), conflict is a universal occurrence in all societies and relationships, often stemming from differing objectives. UNICEF (2016) further describes conflict as a struggle between groups with conflicting aims. Nicholson (1992) characterizes conflict as a complex social phenomenon arising when individuals or groups contend with competing desires, demands, or responsibilities. This contention can lead to zero-sum competition for jobs, housing, trade, and commercial activities in urban environments, creating underlying factors for ethnic conflict (Nnoli, 1978; Otite, 2000; Egwu, 2004). Essentially, such competition is largely driven by ethnic considerations. Ethnic conflict, marked by tensions between different ethnic groups, is complex and rooted in social and political challenges (Banton, 2000). Tepfenhart (2013) describes it as characterized by hostility, often with one ethnic group holding a dominant position. Contributing factors include historical grievances, competition for resources, and cultural or religious disparities (Abasili et al., 2023). In Nigeria,

ethnic loyalty complicates conflict resolution, with unresolved grievances perpetuating cycles of resentment and ethnic violence (Egwu, 2004).

Ethnic Violence in Plateau State

Ethnic Violence results in numerous consequences, with violence being one of its most perilous implications. In Nigeria, ethnic tensions periodically escalate into violence. As noted by Abasili et al. (2023), ethnic conflict in Nigeria generates security risks that can lead to violent outbreaks. This situation raises concerns about potential instability and undermines existing security measures. Moreover, ethnic conflicts represent a significant threat to Nigeria's peace and security, as they can escalate into larger-scale violence or even civil war if not appropriately addressed. The authors' observations are corroborated by Nigeria's history of various ethnic conflicts, which have manifested in different forms of violence, including the civil war known as the Nigerian-Biafran War.

Political Marginalization in Plateau State

Political marginalization refers to the exclusion of specific groups from meaningful participation in political processes and decision-making, often resulting in their voices and interests being overlooked. This exclusion can lead to feelings of disenfranchisement and resentment, exacerbating social tensions and conflicts. In Nigeria, ethnic loyalty and unresolved grievances contribute to political marginalization, complicating efforts for conflict resolution and fostering cycles of ethnic violence (Egwu, 2004; Abasili et al., 2023).

Ethnic Identities in Plateau State

Refer to the shared sense of belonging and collective identity that individuals derive from their ethnic group, characterized by common cultural traits, language, history, and traditions. These identities shape how individuals perceive themselves and others, influencing social interactions, group dynamics, and political behavior. In contexts where ethnic identities are strongly emphasized, they can lead to both solidarity within groups and tension between different ethnic communities, especially in multi-ethnic societies Tepfenhart, T. (2013).

Factors Influencing Ethnic Conflict and Violence in Nigeria

Various factors contribute to ethnic conflict in Nigeria:

Colonial legacy: The colonial powers exacerbated ethnic divisions through their governance strategies, leading to enduring tensions. The British established complete control over what later became Nigeria by annexing different regions: Lagos in 1861, Yoruba-land in 1898, Kamen Boron in 1902, and the Sokoto Caliphate in 1903 (Osagie & Subaru, 2005).

Political factors: Ethnic mobilization by political leaders during military and democratic regimes has intensified conflicts, with electoral fraud further complicating the political landscape. Under the extended military regime, violence against various groups, tribes, and affiliates was permitted and encouraged to achieve predetermined objectives and meet social reform demands. However, the transition to democracy, marred by power-sharing and electoral fraud, exacerbated the situation (Ojo, 2010).

Economic factors: The theorists who share this view believe that competition over scarce resources always catalysis violence and breed it. Competition for scarce resources often leads to violent conflicts among ethnic groups, with economic deprivation breeding social instability (Nnoli, 2010). Furnivall (2009) argued that economic forces generate conflicts between groups with conflicting interests. Generally speaking, this results in a big pool of young people who could be easily recruited for the execution of acts of ethnic or religious violence. This crisis has been exacerbated by inadequate education and a failing educational system in Nigeria (Salawu, 2010).

International influence: The world has become a global village due to globalization, so no one event occurs on its own. The ethno-religious conflicts in Nigeria are no exception to this rule and are linked to several political and religious changes around the world. Global political and religious dynamics have also influenced Nigeria's ethno-religious tensions (Albert, 2001).

Religion: Numerous studies have demonstrated that religion is among the primary catalysts of conflict at the individual and global levels. While this view is widely accepted, it is important to note that one academic, specifically, is considered the primary source of this debate. The idea that religious and cultural identities would be the main drivers of global conflicts in the post-Cold War world was primarily advanced by Samuel Huntington (1993; 1997), who drew inspiration from the works of Lewis (1990). Huntington's viewpoint is the most prominent one on this subject.

Cases of Ethnic Conflict and Violence in Nigeria

Nigeria has witnessed numerous instances of ethnic-induced conflict and violence, deeply rooted in colonial legacies and socio-political dynamics.

Historical context: The colonial government exploited ethnic biases, leading to early violence, such as the 1953 attacks on the Igbo in Kano's Sabon Gari.

Fogged crisis (1982): Tensions arose between the Anglican Hausa Church and the local Muslim community over church expansion, leading to violence when the state government sided with the Muslims. This resulted in the burning of three churches and extensive vandalism (Adejumobi, 2008; Salawu, 2010)

Gideon Akaluka incident (1994): Gideon Akaluka, an Igbo trader, was brutally killed by a Shiite Muslim sect for allegedly desecrating the Holy Quran. The mob's violent act highlighted the tensions between communities, resulting in a mass exodus of non-natives from Kano (Subaru, 2016).

Shagamu violence (1999): The Oro festival in Shagamu escalated into ethnic clashes between the Yoruba and Hausa, causing significant fatalities and property damage, with over 120 vehicles burned and around 100 deaths reported (Usman, 2009).

Kaduna conflicts: Kaduna State has experienced complex ethnic and religious violence, with significant incidents including the Kasuwar Magani (1980) and Zangon Kataf (1984) clashes, illustrating persistent instability in the region (CDD, 2017).

October 2001 protest: A peaceful protest against U.S. military actions devolved into ethno-religious violence, initially blamed on Muslim fundamentalists but rooted in existing tensions, drawing criticism for government inaction (Human Rights Watch, 2001).

Sharia law controversy (1999): The implementation of Sharia law in Zamfara State ignited ethnic conflict in the North, with Governor Alhaji Ahmed Sani Yerima pressuring other states to adopt Sharia amid tensions between Muslim and non-Muslim communities (Adedeji & Ezeabasili, 2018).

Sagamu conflict (1999): A minor incident involving a Hausa woman during an Oro cult ritual escalated into widespread violence, resulting in casualties among both Hausa and Yoruba communities. Despite curfews, retaliatory violence persisted in Kano (Kura, 2010).

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Empirical Review

In September 2001, Jos, the capital of Plateau State in Northern Nigeria, faced significant upheaval, resulting in many deaths and widespread destruction. The conflict pitted Hausa and Fulani Muslims against local Christian communities, surprising many due to Jos's reputation for peace and tourism (Bashir, 2020). Scholars have extensively studied the ongoing ethnic conflict and violence in Plateau State. Uroko (2024) examined the effects of ethno-religious conflict on women's health, revealing that such conflicts worsen physical, emotional, and reproductive health issues, disrupt living conditions and access

to healthcare, and elevate stress and violence against women. Dusu & Oni (2020) analyzed the indigene-settler conflict, concluding that persistent ethnic strife is rooted in primordial ethnic identities and the politicization of grievances by influential actors, emphasizing the importance of assigned ethnic identity and indigenous status. Nyam (2017) investigated the conflict in Jos through qualitative methods and found a significant correlation between ethnic and religious divisions, noting that Hausa/Fulani Muslims make up about 20% of the population, in contrast to the predominantly Christian groups such as Afizere, Anaguta, and Berom. Krause (2011) explored the recurring crises in Jos, attributing them to historical, regional, and religious factors, highlighting the colonial legacy of indirect rule and the resulting divisions between Christian indigenes and Muslim Hausa/Fulani. Higazi (2011) pointed out that ongoing crises arise from political exclusion based on ethnicity and religion, alongside concerns of cultural dominance among Plateau Christians, emphasizing state-community tensions. Ambe-Uva (2010) focused on identity politics and violence in Jos, analyzing the "indigene-settler" conflict, which is driven by political agendas and ethnic rivalries. Despite the breadth of these studies, a crucial gap exists in understanding how these repeating conflicts are sustained by both historical grievances and modern political processes, particularly given their cyclical nature. Many studies focus on either historical or immediate causes of conflict, but they fail to connect how colonial legacies, current political manipulation, and ethno-religious identities interact to perpetuate violence. This study fills that vacuum by investigating the intersections of these elements, providing a more comprehensive approach to understanding ethnic fragmentation and violence in Plateau State.

Theoretical Framework:

Relative Deprivation Theory

This work applies Ted Robert Gurr's (1970) Relative Deprivation Theory, which explains conflict origins through the perceived gap between a group's expectations and the actual benefits received. The theory posits that individuals or groups who feel unfairly deprived compared to a reference group may experience frustration and resentment, leading to social unrest or violence. Crucially, Gurr emphasizes that relative deprivation, rather than absolute deprivation, drives these negative emotions (Gurr, 1970). Factors contributing to feelings of deprivation include social comparison, where individuals assess their resources against others, and group identity, which strengthens bonds within communities. When a group collectively perceives deprivation, it can escalate intergroup conflict. Cultural values, such as individualism and collectivism, also influence reactions to perceived deprivation, with individualistic societies prioritizing personal achievement and collectivist societies focusing on shared resources (Gurr, 1970).

Critics argue that the theory does not fully explain why some deprived individuals avoid conflict or why others, not directly affected, engage in social movements. For example, during the Civil Rights Movement, Black individuals who chose not to participate were labeled "Uncle Toms," a reference to the obedient character in Harriet Beecher Stowe's "Uncle Tom's Cabin" (Duclos, 2001; Curran et al., 2003). The theory also fails to account for participation in movements that do not provide direct benefits, such as the animal rights movement or support from allies in LGBTQ+ activism. Proponents suggest that individuals may join these movements to avoid potential conflicts and hardships, despite the uncertainty of achieving a better life (Gurr, 1970). This perspective highlights the complex motivations behind social movement participation, indicating that the desire for social cohesion can drive individuals to align with marginalized groups.

Relative Deprivation Theory is well-suited to this article's examination of ethnic fragmentation and violence in Plateau State. Ethnic groups in the region perceive political and economic inequalities, fueling conflict. The manipulation of these grievances by political elites, as discussed in the empirical review, fits well within this theory's framework, making it an effective lens for analyzing ethnic violence in the state.

Methodology

This study on Ethnic Fragmentation and violence in Plateau State, Nigeria, employs a mixed-methods approach to comprehensively analyse the complex dynamics of ethnic conflict. The research design integrates both quantitative and qualitative methods, enabling a robust exploration of the underlying factors contributing to ethnic violence.

Qualitative data will be collected through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions with community leaders, local government officials, and residents from various ethnic backgrounds. This will provide nuanced insights into individual and collective experiences of conflict, perceptions of marginalization, and the impact of historical grievances on current tensions. Additionally, participant observation will be utilized in local community meetings and events to gain a deeper understanding of inter-ethnic relations. Quantitative data will be gathered through structured surveys administered to a representative sample of residents in key conflict-affected areas. The survey will focus on variables such as demographics, perceptions of ethnic tension, experiences of violence, and access to resources. This data will be analyzed using statistical software to conduct descriptive and inferential analyses, identifying trends and significant relationships. Qualitative data will

be thematically analyzed, allowing for the identification of key themes and patterns related to ethnic identity, conflict dynamics, and potential pathways for reconciliation.

Study Area

This study focuses on Plateau State, Nigeria, known for its history of ethnic fragmentation and violence. Located in the Middle Belt and bordered by Bauchi, Kaduna, Nasarawa, and Taraba States, Plateau State has a diverse population exceeding 3 million. Divided into 17 Local Government Areas and three Senatorial Zones, the state is home to various ethnic groups, including the Berom, Ngas, Afizere, and Hausa-Fulani. This diversity has historically fuelled competition for resources and political representation, resulting in violent confrontations. Despite its reputation as a "Home of Peace and Tourism," ongoing ethnic conflict—particularly between Christian and Muslim communities—has created an environment of fear and distrust, undermining socio-economic development and peace building efforts. This study aims to explore the dynamics of ethnic fragmentation and violence in Plateau State, contributing insights to the discourse on ethnic conflict in Nigeria. (NEMA, 2012-2014; Nigerian Watch database).

Figure 1: Plateau State Map

Source: Soluap (2022)

Findings

The study showed that there multifaceted factors that cause the ethnic fragmentation, conflict, and violence in Plateau State. The identified factors include unjust geographical boundaries demarcated by the colonial masters, diverse ethnic groups, and competition for resources among settlers, religious differences, and indigene- settler divide.

Some of these factors also appear in the study conducted by Madueke (2018). According to him, the riots in Jos towns and cities occurred because indigenes and settlers were contesting for resources and political power; while famers and Fulani herders were fighting over land in the rural areas. Because of the multifaceted nature of the conflict, Segun, Jegede, & Ajibade (2013) found that the factors reinforce each other. They point out that the Fulanis attributed the conflict to ethnicity and religion. The authors reveal that the Fulani herders argued that their economic prosperity in cattle made them objects of envy by the indigenes. On the contrary, the indigenes said they were not envying the Fulanis; only that the Fulanis were destroying their crops and farmland with their cows.

A similar finding also appears in a study by Enyinnaya (2019) who indicated that the 2008 Jos crisis was triggered by age-long controversy over who will control Jos North Local Government Area between the indigenous natives and the settlers who are Hausa/Fulanis. A study by Krause (2011) still talks about the counterclaims. The author posits that both indigenous communities and the Hausa/Fulanis justify their claims, with the latter arguing that when they entered Jos, it was not a modern city; that they nurtured it to what it is now. On the other hand, the indigenous communities claim that the city was never conquered by Jihadists; that when Dan Fondio came, they resisted him.

The implication of the counterclaims is that each party to the conflict resort to ethno-religious warfare as evidenced in studies by Etim et al (2020) and Uhunmwuango & Aluforo (2011). The former, in their study, found that the ethno-religious

scorecard paved the way for unfair distributions of resources in the state. Moreover, ethno-religious bigots capitalize on the issue to instigate and fan embers of violence in the state.

Conclusion

Qualitative Study on Dynamics of Ethnic Fragmentation and Violence in Plateau State are deeply intertwined with historical, social, economic, political, and religious factors. The persistent contestation over political representation, land ownership, and religious dominance contributes to a growing sense of marginalization among both indigenous populations and settlers. These dynamics create a volatile environment where grievances can rapidly escalate into violence, undermining social cohesion and stability. By understanding the multi-faceted roots of these conflicts, this study highlights the urgent need for targeted interventions that address the underlying causes of ethnic fragmentation and promote lasting peace in Plateau State (Abasili et al., 2023; Egwu, 2004; Dusu & Oni, 2020; Uroko, 2024). Therefore, this study recommends as follows:

Recommendations

1. **Peace Education Program:** The Ministry of Education, in collaboration with relevant organizations, should develop and implement a customized peace education curriculum tailored to the unique socio-cultural dynamics of Plateau State. This curriculum should not only address local dialects but also incorporate religious perspectives, effectively tackling the root causes of conflict and fostering mutual understanding among diverse ethnic groups.
2. **Interfaith Initiatives:** Given the ethno-religious dimensions of the conflict, it is essential for religious stakeholders in Plateau State to establish practical interfaith initiatives and partnerships. State chapters of Christian, Islamic, and African Traditional religions should collaborate to promote peace education and interfaith dialogue, emphasizing shared values of tolerance and coexistence. This collaboration can serve as a platform for addressing misunderstandings and reducing hostility between communities.
3. **Community Dialogue and Mediation:** Community leaders and elders from the conflicting factions should be empowered to form dialogue and mediation committees. These leaders are intimately connected to their communities and possess a deep understanding of the ethnic configurations at play. By leveraging these ethnic connections, they can effectively teach the intricacies of peace education and mediate conflicts. Establishing regular community forums for dialogue can help to build trust, facilitate open communication, and foster a culture of peace.
4. **Policy Advocacy for Inclusive Governance:** It is crucial for policymakers to prioritize inclusive governance that represents all ethnic groups in Plateau State. This involves ensuring equitable access to political representation, land rights, and economic opportunities. By addressing systemic inequalities, the government can reduce feelings of marginalization and resentment among various communities, thereby mitigating the risk of conflict.
5. **Research and Monitoring:** Ongoing research into the dynamics of ethnic conflict in Plateau State should be prioritized, alongside the establishment of monitoring mechanisms to assess the effectiveness of peace initiatives. This will provide valuable data to inform future interventions and ensure that strategies remain relevant and responsive to the evolving context of the region.

By implementing these recommendations, stakeholders can work towards reducing ethnic fragmentation and violence in Plateau State, fostering an environment where diverse communities can coexist peacefully and collaboratively.

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